

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGANDS AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES

Constant		Ligand			
		PMA	SUA	AZA	SEA
$\log K_1^H$		4.36	4.74	5.08	5.23
$\log K_2^H$		2.49	3.86	4.10	3.83

$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	Metal ion	Secondary ligand	Primary ligand			
			NTA	HEDTA	CYDTA	DTPA
	La ^{III}	PMA	5.44	5.38	5.24	5.09
		SUA	3.33	3.26	3.22	3.20
		AZA	3.75	3.60	3.44	3.52
		SEA	5.94	5.83	5.64	5.34
	Pr ^{III}	PMA	5.34	5.29	5.24	5.14
		SUA	3.38	3.32	3.26	3.22
		AZA	4.80	3.65	3.60	3.55
		SEA	6.18	6.08	5.88	5.44
	Nd ^{III}	PMA	6.24	6.14	5.78	5.88
		SUA	3.42	3.35	3.30	3.27
		AZA	3.92	3.40	3.27	3.22
		SEA	6.24	6.13	6.78	5.78

metal ion M(III) appear to be La^{III} > Pr^{III} > Nd^{III}, and with the change in primary ligand the order is NTA > HEDTA > CYDTA > DTPA.

The biocidal characteristics of these mixed ligand chelates formed in solution were tested in aqueous medium at room temperature. The best effects on germination survival and seedling were observed in case of La^{III} as the metal ion and DTPA as the primary ligand.

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Equilibrium Study on Complex Formation of Samarium(III) and Gadolinium(III) with some Amino Acids by Potentiometric Method

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WE report herein the results of our investigation on the stability constants of some amino acid complexes with Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} in aqueous solutions having a fixed ionic strength $I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 25° by potentiometric method¹.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Metal and acid contents of metal solutions were determined by acid-base² and complexometric³ methods. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} using 1 mol dm^{-3} (NaClO₄). An Elico LI-10T pH-meter was employed for pH measurements. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 25° using 0.2 mol dm^{-3} NaOH following the reported procedure^{1,4}. The formation constants (Table 1) have been calculated using method of least-square with the help of a Buzeeby HCL PC/XT computer.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that the formation constant ($\log K_1$) values of Gd^{III} are smaller than those of Sm^{III}. The $\log K_1$ values of Gd^{III} is lower than the earlier

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF A GdIII AND SmIII AMINO ACID COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION*

Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°, Ionic strength = 0.2 mol dm⁻³

Ligand	SmIII		GdIII	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
Valine	5.24	5.04	5.10	4.80
Serine	4.92	3.86	4.66	4.13
Threonine	4.98	4.40	4.64	4.40
Methionine	5.04	4.70	4.93	4.38
Aspartic acid	5.89	4.92	5.65	5.22

* Limits of error ± 0.01 to 0.09.

members of the series. This abnormal behaviour is known as 'gadolinium break'⁵.

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Ultraviolet Spectra of Diphenyl Sulphides, Polyphenylene Sulphides and Polyphenylene Ethers

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THE ultraviolet absorption spectrum of diphenyl sulphide was first recorded by Chaix¹ and later it was studied by several workers²⁻⁴. The compound gives two absorption maxima at 274 (ε 5700) and 250 nm (ε 11800). Finding that the explanations²⁻⁴ given by previous workers for the origin of the bands were at considerable variance, the present investigation was undertaken to make a deeper study of the problem.

The uv spectra of polyphenylene sulphides were also studied with a view to finding their absorption characteristics and to know how the observed bands change with lengthening of the molecule. A comparison of the spectra of polyphenylene ethers with

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their sulphur analogues was also thought of interest. Hence the required polyphenylene ethers were also prepared, their spectra recorded and analysed along with their sulphur analogues.

Experimental

Aryl methyl sulphides were obtained by methylating the corresponding thiophenols with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of alkali: methyl phenyl sulphide, b.p. 190–92° (lit.⁵ 195°/751 mm); methyl *o*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 104°/34 mm (lit.⁶ 96–97°/16 mm); methyl *m*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 110–12°/30 mm (lit.⁷ 110–12.5°/31 mm); methyl *p*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 212° (lit.⁸ 209°/747 mm); methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphide, b.p. 217–18° (lit.⁹ 217–18°).

Diphenyl sulphide was prepared following the reported procedure¹⁰, b.p. 162–63°/18 mm.

General method for the preparation of aryl phenyl sulphides: Freshly-cut sodium (0.1 g atom) was dissolved in absolute ethanol and thiophenol (0.1 mol) was added. Ethanol was then completely evaporated off and the solid aryl sodium was mixed with iodobenzene or the appropriate substituted iodobenzene (0.1 mol) and refluxed (220–30°) in an oil-bath for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was then acidified, treated with zinc dust (10 g) and steam-distilled to remove any unreacted iodo compound and thiol. The residue was ether-extracted, the extract dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and then ether evaporated off and the sulphide was distilled under reduced pressure: phenyl *o*-tolyl sulphide: b.p. 170–72°/22 mm (lit.¹¹ 160.5°/11 mm); phenyl *m*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 164°/10 mm (lit.¹¹ 164.5°/11 mm); phenyl *p*-tolyl sulphide, b.p. 170–72°/20 mm (lit.¹¹ 167.5°/11 mm); *p*-chlorodiphenyl sulphide, b.p. 158–60°/7 mm (lit.⁴ 188°/35 mm); 2,2-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 64° (lit.¹² 64°); 2,2,6-trimethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 89–90° (lit.¹³ 89–90°); 2,2,6,6-tetramethyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 79–80° (lit.¹³ 79–80°); 2,2',6,6'-tetramethoxydiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 152–54° (lit.¹³ 152–54°).

Polyphenylene compounds: The known compounds were prepared according to the reported methods; 1,4-diphenoxybenzene¹⁴, m.p. 76–77°; bis(phenoxyphenyl) ether¹⁴, m.p. 108–09°; bis(*p*-phenoxyphenyl) ether of *p*-hydroxyquinone¹⁵, m.p. 149–50°; 1,4-diphenylthiobenzene¹⁶, m.p. 79–80°; *m*-diphenoxybenzene¹⁴, m.p. 61°.

Bis(p-phenylthiophenyl)sulphide: It was obtained from *p,p'*-dibromodiphenyl sulphide and phenyl sodium sulphide. The required *p,p'*-dibromodiphenyl sulphide was prepared by adding a solution of bromine (18 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) to a solution of diphenyl sulphide (18.6 g) in glacial acetic acid with shaking. The mixture was left for a few hours for complete bromination. The dibromo compound was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 111–12°.